

NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL PHYSIOLOGY

ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ БИОХИМИЧЕСКИХ МАРКЕРОВ ФОСФОРНО-КАЛЬЦИЕВОГО ОБМЕНА И МЕТАБОЛИЗМА КОСТНОЙ ТКАНИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ОСТЕОАРТРОЗОМ

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INDICATORS OF BIOCHEMICAL MARKERS OF PHOSPHORUS-CALCIUM EXCHANGE AND BONE TISSUE METABOLISM IN PATIENTS WITH OSTEOARTHRITIS

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Аннотация

Остеоартрит (ОА) - это дегенеративное заболевание, поражающее суставы и предсуставные ткани, что приводит к снижению качества жизни. В данном исследовании изучается минеральный обмен у пациентов с ОА, выявлено значительное снижение уровня кальция, фосфора и магния, особенно у пациентов с реактивным синовитом. Повышенная активность щелочной фосфатазы способствует резорбции костной ткани и остеопеническим состояниям. Полученные данные подчеркивают необходимость разработки стратегий лечения, направленных не только на устранение симптомов ОА, но и на устранение основных метаболических и биохимических дисбалансов, влияющих на здоровье костей.

Abstract

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a degenerative disease affecting joints and pre-articular tissues, leading to reduced quality of life. This study examines mineral metabolism in OA patients, showing significant decreases in calcium, phosphorus, and magnesium levels, particularly in those with reactive synovitis. Elevated alkaline phosphatase activity contributes to bone resorption and osteopenic conditions. The findings highlight the need for treatment strategies that address not only OA symptoms but also underlying metabolic and biochemical imbalances affecting bone health.

Ключевые слова: Остеоартрит (ОА), минеральный обмен, дефицит кальция, резорбция костной ткани, щелочная фосфатаза.

Keywords: Osteoarthritis (OA), mineral metabolism, calcium deficiency, bone resorption, alkaline phosphatase.

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a systemic disease of joints and pre-articular tissues, traditionally defined as a degenerative process with symptoms of inflammatory disease according to X-ray signs. Osteoarthritis (Osteoarthrosis) is a progressive disease of the musculoskeletal system that leads to a deterioration in the quality of life and disability. The wide spread of osteoarthritis and the social consequences associated with it have raised the issues of improving the diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation of patients with this pathology to the level of medical, social and economic problems(6,7,8). More than 20% of the world's population suffers from OA, 80% of these people have mobility problems, and 30% of people with disabilities are OA sufferers [1,9,10]. OA is a polyetiological disease.

There is no specific reason for the development of this disease. According to L.I.Alekseeva and others (2004), the basis of pathogenesis lies in the imbalance between anabolic and catabolic processes, primarily in the hyaline cartilage and subchondral bone, which are induced (supported) by various factors. It should be

emphasized that OA involves the pathological process, including the synovial membrane, joint capsule, intra-articular ligaments and pre-articular muscles [1].

The aim of the study is to study the status of some indicators of mineral metabolism in patients with OA.

Materials and methods: OA diagnosis was determined based on the nomenclature and classification of the Institute of Rheumatology of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences (1989) and osteoarthrosis classification criteria. 64 (87.8%) of the patients with OA under our control were women and 9 (12.3%) were men. the average age was 48.9. The table showing the clinical characteristics of the examined patients shows that the patients with OA were divided into two subgroups according to their initial status: a) 32 patients (44%) with OA complicated by secondary reactive synovitis and b) 41 patients (56%) with OA not complicated by secondary synovitis). The age of the patients was from 31 to 72 years. The duration of the disease was from 1 to 20 years. In order to determine the stage of OA, the affected joints were examined radiographically. Stage I

was detected in 10 (13.6%), stage II in 32 (43.9%), stage III in 31 (42.5%) patients. According to the clinical form, 90.4% of the patients had gonarthrosis, 9.6% had hip joint arthrosis. It should be noted that the amount of calcium in the plasma is controlled by the skeletal system, which is sensitive to hormonal signals. By reabsorbing phosphate and magnesium, the kidneys

exert the main control over the exchange of these ions, thereby providing a constant calcium level without involving bone tissue. The effect of parathyroid hormone and vitamin D in this process is unquestionable. Vitamin D in its active form supports the bone mass and ensures the delivery of adequate amounts of calcium and phosphorus for the mineralization of new bone.

Table 1

Indicators of mineral metabolism in blood in patients with osteoarthritis

Indicator	Healthy individuals n-20	OA control n-34
Calcium content mmol/l	2.36±0.02	2.07±0.13*
Phosphorus content mMol/l	1.18±0.04	0.89±0.05*
Magnesium content in mmol/	1.0.95±0.07	0.87±0.03
Alkaline phosphatase ED/l	117.5±4.2	215.8±9.71

Note: * - Note: * - R<0.05 is the reliability of differences

Results and discussion: In OA, we observe a decrease in the level of calcium in the blood, which is more pronounced in the combined form of the disease.

Our tests provide information on the total concentration of calcium in ionized and non-ionized forms, although the intracellular concentration of Ca²⁺ ions is much lower and is associated with soluble ligands, cell membranes.

Inorganic phosphorus plays an important role in the metabolism of bone tissue. In the blood serum, inorganic phosphorus is given as NRO42 and N2RO4 ions.

It is known from the results of the examination (Table 1) that the examined patients tend to decrease the amount of phosphorus in their blood, which is more apparent in osteoarthritis.

For example, in patients with OA, the amount of phosphorus in the blood decreases to values of 0.89±0.05 mmol/l, which is 25% lower than the initial values. In the combined form of the disease, the amount

of phosphorus decreases even more and was 0.76±0.02 mmol/l (normally 1.18±0.04 mmol/l), (R<0.05).

It is known that hypophosphatemia develops in vitamin D3 deficiency [5]. Phosphorus absorption disorders are probably associated with chronic liver disease, and may also be a condition of overproduction of parathyroid hormone by the parathyroid glands. Also. With the development of OP, it is possible that its excretion by the kidneys increases in conditions of resorption in bone tissue.

Balanced with vitamin D, magnesium ion is another vital element. The analysis of the obtained results showed a decrease in its amount in the blood, especially in the combined form of the disease, compared to the average of 12-14% in healthy individuals. A less pronounced state of hypomagnesemia can activate parathyroid hormone secretion. It should be pointed out that the ineffectiveness of treatment of hypocalcemia with vitamin D in many cases is due to this same hypomagnesemia [9.12].

Table 2

Indicators of STMZ markers in patients with OA

Indication	Healthy	OA
Osteocalcin (ng/ml)	18.2±2.8	13.9±0.33
B- Cross Labs (ng/ml)	0.22±0.03	0.42±0.02*
P-TH (pg/ml)	34.1±2.3	26.3±2.24*

Note: * - R<0.05 is the reliability of differences with the healthy group

It is known that alkaline phosphatase hydrolyzes pyrophosphate, which has a negative effect on the mineralization process, that is, under these conditions, the enzyme is considered a controller of the calcification process and participates in the formation and mineralization of bone matrix osteoid.

The results of the presented investigation show that in the investigated subjects with OA, the activity of alkaline phosphatase increases reliably and is 270.8±13.0 Ed/l and 272.6±11.2 Ed/l, respectively, which is 2.3 times higher than the initial values. times higher (R<0.05). In recent years, a theory appeared that the changes occurring in the subchondral bone are probably primary and lead to cartilage degradation [5.9].

One of the hypotheses explaining this process is the fact that the subchondral bone produces a large amount of pro-inflammatory cytokines and growth factors, which can enter the overlying tendon (as a result

of the formation of tendon microcracks and vascular invasion of the calcified tendon zone) and degrade the tendon tissue [2.11]. A number of osteotropic hormones (parathyroid hormone, calcitonin, somatotrophic hormone, thyroid and sex hormones) have a systemic effect, their secretion is associated with various directed changes in the concentration of calcium in the blood.

It is known that calcium and phosphorus participate in a number of the most important biochemical functions of the body. Support in the form of an exoskeleton or endoskeleton is required for the body to perform support and movement functions. The body's needs were met in two ways, on the one hand, in the calcium-phosphorus mineral fund (reserve), and on the other hand, due to the development of the endoskeleton, the main function of which is oxyapatite.

Therefore, bone diseases often occur in conditions where calcium and phosphorus homeostasis disorders are covered by bone.

It is known that cellular product - extracellular matrix vesicles are involved in the calcification process. Vesicles store high concentrations of alkaline phosphatase. When the vesicles enter the extracellular space, they begin to accumulate calcium and phosphorus. Calcium absorption probably involves binding to proteoglycans, while phosphorus accumulates due to the action of alkaline phosphatase on pyrophosphates. After that, amorphous calcium phosphate, which turns into oxyapatite in sequence modification, begins to form inside the vesicles. Complex formation plays a central role, which is considered a specific source for oxyapatite proliferation.

It is of particular importance to study the status of markers indicating STMZ disorders in the detection of osteopenic conditions in OA.

Bone tissue metabolism is characterized by two opposite processes: formation of new bone tissue and resorption (degradation) of old tissue. Normally, the amount of newly formed tissue is equal to that which is resorbed. One of the indicators determining bone tissue resorption is blood plasma alkaline phosphatase, collagen degradation product of type I - type I collagen S-telopeptide (CrossLaps), markers of bone tissue formation and bone matrix formation marker - total amino-terminal propeptide of type I procollagen (PINP). is considered

Osteocalcin (gla-protein) is a non-collagenous protein, specific for bone mass and dentin. Osteocalcin is synthesized from osteoblasts and is responsible for the formation of the extracellular matrix of bone. Serum osteocalcin levels are associated with skeletal growth and increase rapidly during bone formation [1.12].

In our research, the study of the status of special markers of osteopenia showed that these indicators have special dynamics. We can see that osteocalcin, the index of bone tissue synthesis, is 1.42 times lower in OA than in the healthy group.

The index of bone tissue resorption increased by 1.9 times in B-Cross Labs OA and was equal to $0.42 + 0.02$ ng/ml on average, which is 2.14 times higher than the values of healthy people ($R < 0, 05$). The same dynamic of changes is also reflected in RNA parameters, in which its amount in patients with OA was on average $26.3 + 2.24$ pg/ml and compared to the parameters of the control group.

It means 22.9% lower ($R < 0.05$) in a relatively statistically reliable way.

Bone mineralization marker with densitometric measurements (Z-criterion) in OA patients was found to be negatively correlated with osteocalcin ($r = -0.39$), and osteocalcin was positively correlated with IF ($r = +0.62$).

When the daily amount of oxyproline in urine, which is an indicator of bone resorption, was checked in patients with OA, its amount was on average $22.4 + 0.28$, which is 1.45 times higher than that of the control group ($R < 0.05$).

Thus, determination of indicators of STMZ markers has gained important diagnostic value in rheumatic

diseases. Violation of STMZ indicators was reflected in the case of all markers. Based on these data, varying degrees of STMZ marker indicators in OA lead to bone resorption, accelerating osteodystrophic processes.

The above-mentioned data indicate that the dynamics of changes in the amount of blood mineral content and enzyme activity in osteoarthritis have a similar nature and depend not only on hormonal status, vitamin D metabolism disorders, but also on many metabolic processes that affect the process of bone formation and decay (resorption).

In OA, we observed a decrease in blood calcium, which was more pronounced when the disease was accompanied by impaired liver function. Similar dynamics were observed in the study of the amount of phosphorus and magnesium in the blood of the subjects. This was not only due to lack of vitamin D, but also due to chronic liver disease.

Alkaline phosphatase activity in subjects with OA was convincingly increased 2.3-fold when co-occurring with chronic liver disease.

Vesicles fall out of the cell and begin to accumulate calcium and phosphorus. Calcium absorption probably involves its binding to acidic phospholipids and proteoglycans, where IF accumulates due to the action of alkaline phosphatase on pyrophosphate. After that, the formation of amorphous calcium phosphate, which is gradually modified into oxyapatite, begins to form inside the vesicles.

Thus, in patients with OA, changes in blood mineral composition, determined dynamics of enzyme activity are of the same nature and are not only related to calcium-phosphorus changes in blood content, hormonal status disorders, vitamin D metabolism, but also affect the process of bone formation and resorption in osteopenic disorders. It is also related to the functional state of the liver, where many metabolic processes take place.

Based on the knowledge about the pathogenesis of OA, the treatment of this chronic progressive joint disease can be limited to: reducing pain and inflammation, reducing the number of sprains and new joint damage, improving the quality of life, slowing the progression of OA and preventing disability, pathogenetic treatment of OA as well as restores the normal structure of the hyaline cartilage, stops catabolic processes and improves the mineral composition of bone tissue by activating the synthesis of valuable glycosaminoglycans and type II chondrocyte collagen.

Conclusion: the detected disturbances in the parameters of mineral metabolism in OA patients indicate the potential risk of polyorgan disorders, which is undoubtedly one of the pathogenetic mechanisms that allow the disease to worsen. This situation requires constant monitoring of metabolic disorders in patients with OA.

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